

Predominating Problems Occurring in Patients Provided with Long-Term Domestic Care in Their Home Environment During the Period of 2005-2006

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Abstract

A chronic patient who is disabled and spends many years at home feels physical and psychic discomfort. As a result of loss of health he feels helpless, lost and alone. He expects support and help from his family, friends and health service. He receives support from the nurse working in long term domestic care who looks after him and solves his problems in his environment/home where he should feel safe. Presentation of the health problems of patients staying at their homes who make use of the specialist care services performed free by the graduate nurses. Discussion on the role of the nurse working in long-term domestic care who is aimed at helping to solve the health problems in chronic and disabled patients. The research material was collected from the pilot studies of 40 persons provided with long term domestic care. The studies were carried out on 20 patients living in the Lublin province and 20 patients living in the Silesian province between September 2005 and January 2006. One of the predominating problems encountered in patients provided with long term domestic care is that of incontinence of urine and feces. The other vital question is indication for carrying out regular dressings of badly healing wounds, decubitus ulcers and trophic ulcers of the shanks.

Our studies demonstrate that the patients expect a regular and continuous care from the nurse and that they feel helpless and endangered when they deteriorate.

Keywords: chronic patient, disabled person, nurse services

Introduction

Chronic and disabled patient staying long years at home feels psychological and physical discomfort. After loss of his health he feels helpless, lost and left alone. He expects support and aid from his family, friends and the health service. He receives support from the nurse working in the long-term domestic care that is caring him and solves his problems at his home/environment where he should feel safe. In order to understand the disabled persons one should comprehend their difficulties and achievements in defeating the barriers of everyday life [1, 2, 14]. The health problems of the patient provided with the long-term domestic care are diagnosed on the basis of the

nurse diagnosis. The formulation of the nurse diagnosis has the fundamental value for the individualized nursing, because it clearly shows what is the state of the subject of care with whom the nurse will deal with. Finding the determined state (which is equivalent with putting forward the diagnosis) will require to take the exact action, at first of the decision-making, and then of the executive character. The nurse should decide whether one should strive to: change the already recognized state of health or keep up the state of health at the recognized level. Making a nurse diagnosis is a responsible and difficult task. It requires a good preparation, a long experience, a logical thinking and a proper drawing conclusions from the ensuing situation [4]. Further activities of the nurse performing the

long term domestic care are concerned with the planning of the nursing process for the patient that has been included in such a form of care [3]. The process of nursing that is planned, realized and systematically assessed permits to choose proper methods of the nursing that are individually adjusted for each patient. The process of nursing that was introduced and consistently conducted by the nurse at home of the chronic and disabled patient has the following goals: strengthening the state of health which patient has at his disposal, caring the patient's health by the conducted health education, consistent diagnosing the threats to health, reinforcing the positive behaviours, involving family and friends into activities building up the health, developing the patient's skills for active and creative life, involving family in an active and creative style of patient's life [10].

Aims of Work

1. Presentation of the health problems of the patients living at their homes who are provided with the free specialist caring services performed by graduate nurses.
2. Discussion on the role of nurse in long-term domestic care who has to help to solve health problems of the chronic and disabled patients.

Material and Methods

The research material was collected on the basis of the pilot studies carried out in 40 persons provided with long-term domestic care by the graduate nurses. The studies were performed on 20 patients living in the Lublin province and 20 patients from the Silesian province in the period from September 2005 to January 2006. Both groups of patients were chosen in such a way as to differentiate the health problems appearing in these two provinces. Since the long-term domestic care in the Silesian province developed earlier it is thriving and embraces much larger population requiring this type of the health services. On the other hand, in the Lublin province the long-term domestic service can include much smaller number of patients because of the shortage of the financial means received from the National Health Fund. This happens despite great needs resulting from the state of health of the patients living at their homes and not qualified for the institutional care.

Results

The chronic and disabled persons included into the long-term domestic care were asked whether they feel excluded from the normal life. The analysis of the sense of exclusion from the normal life shows important differences between the patients living in the Silesian and the Lublin province. The positive response (yes) was obtained in

55% of patients living in the Silesian province and only in 40% of patients living in the Lublin province. There was also difference in feeling the degree of the exclusion between two groups of patients. A slight sense of exclusion was felt by 15% of the respondents from the Lublin province and by none of respondents from the Silesian province. This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), (Table 1). Taking into consideration the category of the diseases of the patients provided with long term domestic care the two compared groups were asked about the sense of limitation concerning the range of the free movement. No significant differences were found between patients of the two groups. 100% of patients from the Silesian province and 95% of patients from the Lublin province responded that they have sense of limitation as concerns the range of the free movement (Table 2). The state of health of the studied persons suggested the next question which concerned the problem of urinary and fecal incontinence. The answers showed that the problem appeared in 95% of patients in the Silesian province and in smaller number of patients in the Lublin province (80%). The lack of troubles with urinary and fecal incontinence was reported by only 1% of patients in the Silesian province and 4% of patients in the Lublin province. The differences between

Table 1. Sense of exclusion from normal life.

	Silesian province		Lublin province	
	N	%	N	%
Yes, to a considerable degree	2	10.00	3	15.00
Yes, considerably	11	55.00	8	40.00
Yes, of average degree	3	15.00	3	15.00
Yes, slightly	0	0.00	3	15.00
No	4	20.00	3	15.00
Total	20	100.00	20	100.00
χ^2	2.368			
p	<0.05			

Table 2. Sense of limitation concerning the range of free movement.

	Silesian province		Lublin province	
	N	%	N	%
Yes	20	100.00	19	95.00
No	0	0.00	1	5.00
Total	20	100.00	20	100.00
χ^2	0.025			
p	>0.05			

two groups were statistically significant (Table 3). Frequently the urinary and fecal incontinence are the cause of

and in 15% answered "no". These percentages for patients in the Lublin province were 65% and 35%, respectively.

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